

A Study of Influence of Adversity Quotient on Academic Achievement of Adolescents Stage

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Abstract

Adversity Quotient (AQ) is the capacity to adjust with the adversities in life. A person with good Adversity Quotient can achieve the goal by fighting against all odds. It is also related to many other factors like self-esteem, motivation, fighting spirit, creativity, sincerity, positive attitude, optimism, emotional stability etc. Adversity quotient is also related to the Academic problems of students. This study is conducted to find out the relationship between adversity quotient and academic achievement of adolescents students (secondary school students). The method used was survey and the sample was a random sample of 566 student of Varanasi city. The value of correlation co-efficient obtained for adversity quotient and academic achievement ($r = 0.69$, significant at 0.05 level) shows that the two variables are closely related.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Adversity Quotient

Introduction

Everyone's life is full of problems today, whether it is a child or an old man, an adverse situation has surrounded him. If we talk about the adolescent stage here, then they have to face the adverse situation more because this is their transition period, here they are neither considered as children nor adults. That's why Stanley Hall called the adolescent age the stage of stress and storm. Here there is a lot of family pressure, social pressure as well as academic pressure on them, and due to the increased pressure, if they are not able to do well in academics, then they go into depression increases so much that it takes the form of suicidal tendency which is not right. Due to excessive stress, instead of doing well in academics, they do worse, so that they can do well in the field. For this Paul Stoltz has given a term which is known as Adversity Quotient (AQ).

Concept of Adversity Quotient

Adversity Quotient (AQ) refers to the ability of an individual to handle unpleasant or adverse situations. For many years, researchers have devoted a great deal of their studies to Intelligence Quotient (IQ) and Emotional Quotient (EQ), which are considered to be determinants of success and superior accomplishment but the need for this can be illustrated by the fact that students with the same

Intelligence Quotient does not always respond in the same way to identical situations. In the context of the teaching-learning process, it has been observed over time that some students, in spite of facing insurmountable odds; somehow keep going, while others are weighed down by the avalanche of changes within their environment. This implies that there are other underlying factors that are responsible for forging ahead despite the changes. Researchers like Stoltz (1997, 2010) identified the Adversity Quotient (AQ) as one of such psychological variables, which tells how well one withstands adversity and one's ability to triumph over it. In fact, more researches recently have shown that measurement of AQ is a better index in achieving success than IQ, education or even social skills (Zhou, 2009, Tantor, 2007).

By understanding the concept of AQ we can better understand how we and others react to challenge and adversity in all aspects of our lives. In fact, how people respond to adversity is a strong indicator of ability to succeed in many endeavors/areas.

Definitions of Adversity Quotient (AQ)

“The capacity of the person to deal with the adversities of his life. As such, it is the science of human resilience.” (Paul Stoltz, 1997)

How a person reacts to adversity has been described as his adversity response and is measured by his adversity quotient. An individual's response to adversity may be

determined by personal characteristics and environmental factors. Studies conducted by Stoltz (2010) showed that one's response to adversity is formed through the influence of parents, teachers, peers and other key people. Furthermore, people's response to adversity can be interrupted and permanently changed, due to some factors. Studies, particularly the study by Dweck (2012) have shown that responses to adversity are learned.

Stoltz (1997, 2010) attested to the fact that students of every age group face different adversities unique to them with respect to time and place. This struggle against adversities according to him continues even after school into adult life. He affirmed in one of his studies that the number of adversities an individual faces each day on an average has increased from seven (7) to twenty three (23) in the last 10 years, with the students population not being exempted. Students need to cope up with these pressures/stressors in life. Hence the need is felt, for education to provide the necessary help/guidance to the students to cope up with these situations and face these adversities and come out of it unscratched successfully. Thus discovering and measuring AQ and factors that influence it allows one to understand how and why some people consistently exceed the predictions and expectations of their natural intellectual ability.

According to Stoltz, one's Adversity Quotient (AQ) consists of four dimensions: CORE. This short form includes Control, Ownership, Reach and Endurance.

C = Control Control is the degree to which one perceives they can influence whatever happens next. It influences the direction of action, amount of effort, level of perseverance and resilience. It determines resilience, health, and tenacity. People with high score on control will have better control of any adverse situation they may encounter.

O = Ownership Ownership is how much one feels accountable to improve the adverse situation. This determines accountability, responsibility, action and engagement. People with high score on ownership will feel accountable of the situation they are in. They will take responsibility, learn from that experience and change their strategy to try a new route and take action.

R = Reach It is the degree to which one perceives an adversity will affect other aspects of their life. It determines burden and stress; it tends to have a cumulative effect. People with high reach scores see the adversity in a different view. They do not allow the adversity to hinder other parts of their life. They believe adversity caters to only that particular situation and does not impact other aspects of life.

E = Endurance Endurance is the duration the individual perceives the adversity will last. It determines hope, optimism, and willingness to persevere. People with high endurance score find that adversities are temporary and believe that there is always a solution to overpower the adversity.

Those four elements combine to form a person's AQ and his or her response to any given adversity. CORE dimensions are grounded on research and breakthroughs in three scientific fields: namely Cognitive Psychology, Psychoneuroimmunology, and Neurophysiology.

1) Cognitive psychology (control and mastery of one's life) - informs us that people differ on a continuum in what adversity can do to them and this depends largely on how they react to adversity.

2) Psychoneuroimmunology (immune function) is a field in science that examines the mind-body relationship. In essence, it studies the relationship between what one thinks and feels and what goes on in the body. How do thoughts and feelings affect the body and its overall health? It indicates that there is a direct link between one's response to adversity and health both physical and mental.

3) Neurophysiology (science of the brain) is a field in science that focuses on the brain. It studies how the brain learns and functions. How habits formed and what are must occur to change habits once they are established? It indicates that man is a creature of habit and all habits are learned.

He draws an analogy with the life threatening, physical adversities that a mountaineer may face. On the basis of their response to the adversity people may be classified as climbers, campers or quitters.

- *Climbers* are described as people who even in the face of severe adversity even when they seem to be almost wiped out will have the

physical and mental strength to get up collect themselves make best use of their resources and move on to survive.

- *Campers* on the other hand are the ones who when faced by an adversity will use all their resources to merely somehow hold on to the positions they are at without active effort to move on to a better position.
- *Quitters* are the ones who give up. They will allow the adversity to overtake them and let the events take their own course without conscious and deliberate effort to do something about it.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the relationship between Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievement of secondary school students.
- To compare the levels of Adversity Quotient (AQ) of secondary school students with reference to their gender.
- To study the relationship between component of Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievement of secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievement of secondary school students.

Ho2: There is no significant difference of Adversity Quotient of boys and girls students.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between components of Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievement of secondary school students.

Methodology

The purpose of this study was to find out “the influence of Adversity Quotient with Academic Achievement”. Considering the nature of study Descriptive Survey was considered most appropriate.

Population

In this study, the population consists of all Secondary School Students of C.B.S.E of Varanasi City.

Sample

In this study, ‘Simple random sampling’ technique has been employed for drawing sample from the population.

Students are randomly selected from twenty one CBSE secondary schools in Varanasi city. A total of 566 students from all the twenty one schools (308 boys and 258 girls) constitute the sample of the study. Sample comprised of class IX and X students of 2017 and 2018 session only.

Tool used in the study

Adversity Quotient Scale (AQS) This scale was developed by the researcher to know the Adversity Quotient of the secondary school students. The AQS consists of 20 items. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined by the test-retest method and found to be .78. The construct validity of AQS was established by factor analysis.

Data collection

Data collection was done from schools of Varanasi during the period 2017-2018.

First of all, before the collection of data the investigator contacted the Principal of selected schools to take the permission for data collection, by explaining the purpose of the study. They were assured that the data would be used for research purpose only and the responses would be confidential. After getting permissions of the principal and winning the confidence of the students. All possible efforts were made to ensure the best possible conditions for administrating the questionnaire and scale and to make sure students felt at ease and responded to the tools with full concentration.

Analysis of data

In order to arrive at meaningful inferences related to objectives of the present study, descriptive statistics- mean, median, mode, standard deviation and inferential statistic-factor analysis, Karl Pearson’s correlation coefficient, t-test were used on 0.05 level of significance. Excel and SPSS version 20 was used for statistical analysis of data.

Objective wise findings of the study

This section presents objective wise summary of findings derived after analysis and interpretation of data.

Finding related to the objective 1

Table No. 1 showing correlation between Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

S. N O	Variables	Coefficient of Correlation	Significance level (2-tailed)	Null hypothesis Not Rejected / Rejected
1	Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievements	0.69*	Significant	Rejected

- The acquired product moment coefficient of correlation ($r = 0.69$). It means high and positive coefficient correlation between adversity quotient and academic achievement of secondary school students in Varanasi city. Therefore the null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no significant correlation between the Adversity quotient and Academic achievement of secondary school students in Varanasi city is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Finding related to the objective 2

Table 2 showing comparison of Adversity

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t value	Remark
Boy	308	67.62	13.07	1.08	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Girl	258	68.80	12.94		

Quotient of Boys and Girls in terms of Mean, S.D., and 't' Values

- Male and female students of secondary schools do not differ significantly on the basis of adversity quotient (t - value (1.08)=,df=564) at 0.05 level of significance.

Finding related to the objective 3

- Each four component of Adversity Quotient are found to be significantly correlated with Academic Achievement (0.61, 0.60, 0.61, 0.29). Therefore the null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no significant correlation between the

components of Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievement of secondary school students in Varanasi city is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3 showing correlation between components of Adversity Quotient and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students

S. N O	Components of Adversity Quotient	Coefficient of Correlation	Significance level (2-tailed)	Null hypothesis Not Rejected/ Rejected
1	Control	*0.61	Significant	Not Rejected
2	Origin	*0.60	Significant	Not Rejected
3	Reach	*0.61	Significant	Not Rejected
4	Endurance	*0.29	Significant	Not Rejected

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Conclusion

The present study was designed to assess the influence of adversity quotient on academic achievement of secondary school students.

The study found positive correlations between AQ and academic achievement (0.69). This confirms the findings of Mwivanda, Marycasta(2016),Bakare (2015), Zhou Huijuan (March, 2009) and Rochelle D’Souza (2006) where it was found that there is a significant relationship between adversity quotient and academic performance of secondary school students and AQ was found to be a successful predictor of students’ academic achievement for the total sample from different types of schools. Thus students who have the capacity to successfully face adverse life experiences are better performers than that of those who do not successfully deal with the unpleasant life experiences.

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